

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 11th – 17th January 2021

www.covid19bibliometrics.org

A. Medicine and Health

January 15, 2021 (JAMA Int Med)

Comparison of Saliva and Nasopharyngeal Swab Nucleic Acid Amplification Testing for Detection of SARS-CoV-2: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

Guillaume Butler-Laporte, Alexander Lawandi, Ian Schiller et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.8876>

This systematic review and meta-analysis assessed the diagnostic accuracy of saliva nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT) for diagnosis of COVID-19. The authors found that saliva NAAT had a similar sensitivity and specificity to that of nasopharyngeal NAAT, suggesting that saliva NAAT represents an appealing alternative to nasopharyngeal swab NAAT and may strengthen massive testing efforts.

January 14, 2021 (JAMA Ophthalmol.)

Progression of Myopia in School-Aged Children After COVID-19 Home Confinement

Jiaxing Wang, Ying Li, David C. Musch et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2020.6239>

This cross-sectional study compares the prevalence of myopia in school-aged children 5 years before the COVID-19 pandemic with the prevalence during home confinement due to the pandemic. They found that home confinement due to the COVID-19 pandemic was associated with a substantial myopic shift in children.

January 14, 2021 (JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg)

Socioeconomic Disparities in Patient Use of Telehealth During the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Surge

Ilaaf Darrat, Samantha Tam, Marwan Boulis

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoto.2020.5161>

This cohort study assesses demographic and socioeconomic factors associated with patient participation in telehealth visits during the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic.

January 13, 2021 (The NEJM)

Convalescent Plasma Antibody Levels and the Risk of Death from Covid-19
Michael J. Joyner, Rickey E. Carter, Jonathon W. Senefeld et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2031893>

Among more than 3000 hospitalized patients with COVID-19, recipients of high-titre convalescent plasma had lower mortality at 30 days than recipients of low-titre plasma. The effect of high-titre plasma was greatest in the subgroup of patients who were not receiving mechanical ventilation.

January 11, 2021 (Nat Commun)

Antibody neutralization of SARS-CoV-2 through ACE2 receptor mimicry.

Ge, J., Wang, R., Ju, B. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20501-9>

The authors perform in-depth structural and functional analysis of three potent yet variable neutralizing antibodies of SARS-CoV-2. They describe their results and identified one antibody, P2C-1F11 that most closely mimics the binding of receptor ACE2, displays the most potent neutralizing activity in vitro and conferred strong protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection in Ad5-hACE2-sensitized mice. Their results offer a structural and functional basis for potent neutralization via disruption of the very first and critical steps for SARS-CoV-2 cell entry.

January 11, 2021 (The Lancet Resp Medicine)

Development and validation of the ISARIC 4C Deterioration model for adults hospitalised with COVID-19: a prospective cohort study

Rishi K Gupta, Ewen M Harrison, Antonia Ho et al.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(20\)30559-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(20)30559-2)

Gupta et al. developed and validated a multivariable logistic regression model for in-hospital clinical deterioration for inpatients with highly suspected or confirmed COVID-19. The 4C Deterioration model was found to have strong potential for clinical utility and generalisability to predict clinical deterioration and inform decision making among adults hospitalised with COVID-19.

January 8, 2021 (Genet Med)

“It seems like COVID-19 now is the only disease present on Earth”: living with a rare or undiagnosed disease during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Halley, M.C., Stanley, T., Maturi, J. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41436-020-01069-7>

This study aims to identify specific impacts of the pandemic on patients with rare and undiagnosed diseases (RUD) and targets for improving support and health-care access. Using an online survey, they identified specific, serious challenges affecting RUD patients and families during the COVID-19 pandemic, calling attention to develop approaches to mitigate these challenges both during and beyond the pandemic.

January 7, 2021 (Nat Commun)

Optimal COVID-19 quarantine and testing strategies.

Wells, C.R., Townsend, J.P., Pandey, A. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20742-8>

The authors develop a mathematical model that quantifies the probability of post-quarantine transmission incorporating testing into travel quarantine, quarantine of traced contacts with an unknown time of infection, and quarantine of cases with a known time of exposure. They show that appropriately timed testing can make shorter quarantines effective.

B. Science and Engineering

January 28, 2020 (Physica Medica)

A patient-specific approach for quantitative and automatic analysis of computed tomography images in lung disease: application to COVID-19 patients

L. Berta, C. De Mattia, F. Rizzetto *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2021.01.004>

The researchers proposed a patient-independent model for the estimation of the well-aerated volume of lungs in CT images. They then applied a Gaussian fit to the lower CT histogram data to provide the estimation of the well-aerated lung volume. Independence from CT reconstruction parameters and the respiratory cycle was analysed using healthy lung CT images and 4DCT acquisitions. The Gaussian metrics and first-order radiomic features calculated for a third cohort were compared with healthy lungs. Each lung was further segmented and a new biomarker derived from Gaussian fit parameter was proposed to represent the local density changes.

They found that healthy subjects were significantly different from COVID-19 patients for all the metrics calculated. Graphical representation of the local biomarker provides spatial and quantitative information in a single 2D picture. They concluded that this model was able to consider the inter-and intra-subject variability and defined a local biomarker to quantify the severity of the disease.

January 14, 2021 (European Journal of Radiology)

Multi-classifier-based identification of COVID-19 from chest computed tomography using generalizable and interpretable radiomics features

Lu Wang, Brendan Kelly, Edward H. Lee *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2021.109552>

The researchers aimed to identify radiomic features that were significantly associated with the classification of COVID-19 pneumonia using multiple classifiers. 10 positive and 108 negative patients were retrospectively recruited from three hospitals. They used four classifiers (linear classifier, k-nearest neighbour, least absolute shrinkage and selection operator [LASSO],

and random forest) to differentiate positive and negative patients. Using the Pyradiomics technique, 120 radiomic features were extracted from each image. The key radiomic features screened by different classifiers lead to significant differences in classification accuracy. The LASSO achieved the best performance on the external validation dataset and attained good agreement (Kappa score: 0.89) with radiologists (sensitivity: 75.6%, specificity: 78.2%, and AUC: 0.81).

January 11, 2021 (Safety Science)

Diagnostic model for the society safety under COVID-19 pandemic conditions
Costas A. Varotsos, Vladimir F. Krapivin & Yong Xue.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105164>

The authors developed an information-modeling method for assessing and predicting the consequences of the pandemic. They performed a detailed analysis of official statistical information. The method is based on the algorithm of multi-channel big data processing. COVID-19 data are analyzed using an instability indicator and a system of differential equations describing four groups of people: susceptible, infected, recovered and dead. Stochastic processes induced by COVID-19 are assessed with the instability indicator showing the level of stability of official data and the reduction of the level of uncertainty. Their findings show that COVID-19 divides the global population into three groups according to the relationship between Gross Domestic Product and the number of infected people.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

January 23, 2021 (Government Information Quarterly)

Does government social media promote users' information security behavior towards COVID-19 scams? Cultivation effects and protective motivations
Zhenya Tang, Andrew S. Miller, Zhongyun Zhou et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2021.101572>

Cybercriminals are taking advantage of the COVID-19 outbreak and offering COVID-19-related 'scams' or fraudulent deals to unsuspecting people. This study highlights the importance of government social media for information security management during crises.

January 20, 2021 (Journal of Psychiatric Research)

Workplace violence and its association with quality of life among mental health professionals in China during the COVID-19 pandemic
Xiao-Meng Xie, Yan-Jie Zhao, Feng-Rong An et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2021.01.023>

This study found that workplace violence was common among mental health professionals in China during the COVID-19 pandemic. Unsurprisingly the

authors conclude that “appropriate measures” to prevent workplace violence should be developed.

January 12, 2021 (Social Sciences & Humanities Open)

How England first managed a national infection crisis: Implementation of the Plague Orders of 1578 compared with COVID-19 Lockdown March to May 2020

Graeme Toby

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2021.100111>

This paper draws comparisons between the current COVID-19 pandemic and the first-ever national management of epidemic infection in England - the Plague Orders of 1578. The author notes that then as now, limits on freedom of movement and congregation, social distancing and quarantine measures were applied for the sake of preserving life, loss of livelihood was ameliorated by government loans and inconvenient opinions suppressed. The increased danger in certain necessary occupations and flight to second homes by the rich have also been observed, with health inequities uncovered and restrictions on being with the dying and burying the dead enforced.

The paper does not directly address how technology was and is applied to respond to the pandemic then and now but provides the memorable conclusion: “In a wider biopsychosocial (*sic*) sense, epidemic disease is not a leveller of society and we are not all in the same boat with coronavirus”. Indeed.

January 4, 2021 (Social Science & Medicine)

Can a COVID-19 vaccine live up to Americans’ expectations? A conjoint analysis of how vaccine characteristics influence vaccination intentions

Matt Motta

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113642>

This US study considers how properties of vaccines themselves (e.g., national origin, efficacy, risk of side effects) might influence vaccination intentions. This information can help public health officials preempt differential intentions to vaccinate, and inform health communication campaigns that encourage vaccine uptake.

Unsurprisingly US respondents prefer vaccines that are US-made, over 90% effective, and carry a less than 1% risk of minor side effects. This is potentially problematic, as some leading vaccine candidates are produced outside the US, and/or may be more likely to produce minor side effects than respondents would otherwise prefer. Worryingly, intended vaccine refusal rates exceed 30% for a vaccine meeting these optimal characteristics.